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Giving Voice to a Caribbean History of Migration - “The Enigma of Arrival: The Politics and Poetics of Caribbean Migration to Britain”

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Abstract

In 2018, The University of the West Indies (UWI) and The Barbados Museum & Historical Society (BMHS) with funding support from EU-LAC MUSEUMS, embarked on a project coordinated by the University of St. Andrews (USTAN) to facilitate a community-led composite history, of the Caribbean migratory experience to Britain, and its role in multi-regional exchanges. The Enigma of Arrival: The Politics and Poetics of Caribbean Migration to Britain, is significant as a rare Caribbean-based exhibition on post war migration from the Caribbean territories to Britain and then the subsequent post-independence rejection of Caribbean migrants. This collaborative effort was an attempt to record and “publish” a missing or “silenced” part of our shared Caribbean history. The exhibit utilized a community of curatorial practice through a combination of multi-vocal, co-curatorial methods with “poetics” – language and cultural expressions through literature, music, theatre and visual art based on primary and secondary research. This paper will chronicle and examine the conceptualization, research and development of the exhibition and its content as it pertains to several themes explored in Caribbean history, and the effectiveness of using a community of curatorial practice in the exhibition methodology.

In 2018, The University of the West Indies (UWI) and The Barbados Museum & Historical Society (BMHS) with funding support from EU-LAC MUSEUMS¹, embarked on a project coordinated by the University of St. Andrews to facilitate a community-led composite history, of the Caribbean migratory experience to Britain, and its role in multi-regional exchanges. Its importance to world history and politics at the time could not be overstated given the ongoing Windrush Migration scandal within Britain and the worldwide outcry of the Caribbean diaspora communities without.

The Enigma of Arrival: The Politics and Poetics of Caribbean Migration to Britain, is significant as a rare Caribbean-based exhibition on post war migration from the Caribbean territories to Britain and then the subsequent post-independence rejection of Caribbean migrants. This collaborative effort was an attempt to record and “publish” a missing or “silenced” part of our shared Caribbean History – our history of migration to Britain. The exhibit, based on primary and secondary research from a number of sources and resources including first-hand oral history accounts of the experience and records from the West Indies Federal Archives utilised a combination of multi-vocal, co-curatorial methods with “poetics” – language and cultural expressions through literature, music, theatre and visual art.

This paper will chronicle and examine the conceptualization, research and development of the exhibition and its content as it pertains to several themes explored in Caribbean history, including:

- The Challenges in/of Caribbean History: Historiographies, Historical Constructions and Reception
- Caribbean Collaboration and Cooperation
- Migration and Movements in the Caribbean
- The Fall of Empire, Brexit and the Caribbean

Introduction/Background

“When I was growing up, being one of the first, one of the only black families in the area, and all my friends were white. I didn’t really feel as though I fitted in with their world, but at the same time I didn’t know much about where my parents came from. You know I’ve never been to Barbados. I’ve heard a lot about it, from my family and friends of family and I’d like to visit, but it doesn’t feel to me like home. When my parents speak of home, I can’t imagine myself, I’d never describe it as home. I don’t feel that my connections are that strong to Barbados, but at the same time I don’t feel as though I belong here. I don’t regard myself as English. I’ve looked at calling myself British, but I don’t feel as though I belong, I don’t feel as if I’m wanted here, and I feel like I’m caught between two cultures, and I’m trying to find where I belong. I think you always need to make like a pilgrimage, to Barbados, to find, where I belong. And in a way I’m scared to do that, in case it’s not home, well where will I belong? How do I discover myself? What’s my identity? I’m a black woman, but am I British or am I West Indian? Barbadian? I don’t know, I just get very confused.” (Source: Transcript of 1997 interview – Claude Graham’s “Second Generation” television series)

In the seventy or so years since the landing of the Empire Windrush on British soil disgorging assorted British subjects of West Indian descent to assist with the efforts at rebuilding British Post-war society, little has been recorded about the impact this mass migration of tens of thousands had on the society they left or the one where they settled. Modern day Britain is populated by the descendants of these British subjects but little of their stories are known beyond the horrors recently exposed in the journalism surrounding the “Windrush Scandal”.

The pursuit of Caribbean history in the 21st century has been largely a process of dismantling and of decentralization as former colonial subjects have attempted to redress the silences inherent in a western narrative in the telling of our stories. The need for the recognition of the colonial “other” as a being with his or

her own story to tell and acknowledge has been central to the thinking and writing of some of the region's revolutionaries such as Trouillot, James, Hall and Fanon since the middle of the last century. However, with hundreds of years of slavery and dissonance behind us it has been left largely to the historians of the current century to build on the foundations of their philosophies and document those histories and the many stories which remain untold. It is at the nexus of one such untold story that the "Enigma of Arrival" has its genesis.

The EU-LAC Museums project has its roots in a desire and commitment to the "idea that fostering inter-cultural dialogue and creativity through...regional and community museums is fundamental" to "develop associated history and theory"². Understanding that there exists in Europe a "crisis of identity, seeking to define its past, present, and future position in relation to the wider world, and consolidate regional cohesion across generations within a wider global community", the project takes advantage of "societal opportunities" primarily as an acknowledged space within history which would benefit from a more integrated understanding of how these smaller post-colonial communities have shaped and affected the European metropolises. The project work package specifically identified the following:

- Construction and development of a research agenda, network and schedule enabling the project to compile, produce, share new research resources with all potential users, either institutional professionals, or as communities and public in general.
- Empowerment of institutional partners within the EULAC project with the necessary digitisation and communication technology training and tools allowing them to fully participate in and support the development of a virtual museum of the migration experience/s as informed by the experiences and trajectories outlined.

- Conceptualisation and development of new interpretation resources, utilising both historical and contemporary constructs (both memory and art based) in the development of travelling exhibitions and associated educational resources, making available through partnership arrangements with museums as identified³.

The Barbados Museum & Historical Society as a participating organization in the EULAC Museums project at the behest of the University of the West Indies, a member of the project's consortium, embarked on a series of activities aimed at taking on-board a number of objectives for expansion of the body of knowledge which currently represents Caribbean history of post War migration:

1. Increasing the knowledge area of EU-CELAC relations in the museum world by researching the concepts and experiences of sustainability in museums and communities in the two regions, with a special focus on heritage technologies and histories of migration as they relate to these communities
2. Enhancing sustainable development and social inclusiveness in remote rural and island locations through dialogue between academics, policy makers, museums, and communities
3. Creating a common and sustainable vision for community museums
4. Making available and celebrating knowledge generated by the project to potential users, museum professionals, and decision makers via online accessibility and extensive dissemination efforts
5. Rigorous evaluation of project methodologies and outcomes with a view to creating a sustainable model for ongoing development of similar resources and maintenance of the relationships created by the programme⁴.

To fulfil these objectives a number of specific tasks were assigned which would have bearing on the genesis of the body of research and the creation of the creation of its primary outputs, namely the Virtual Museum of Caribbean Migration and Memory (VMCMM)⁵, the International Museums Conference Itinerant Identities: Community Museums/Museum Communities and the travelling exhibit *The Enigma of Arrival: The Politics and Poetics of Caribbean Migration to Britain*.

In addition, an art exhibit Arrivants: Art and Migration in the Anglophone Caribbean World, was staged which explored:

“...the diasporic nature of Caribbean society as documented and interrogated through its artistic production... at different points in time from the mid twentieth century to the present day and on the cultural impact of migration from and to the United Kingdom, and by extension Europe and to North America, as well as the movements within the Caribbean and Central American region. In doing so, we also consider the earlier histories of forced and voluntary migration, that have become deeply embedded in the psyche of Caribbean peoples, and the manner in which these have shaped the identities and experiences of Caribbeans today, whether they are (or are not) themselves migrants. Most of all, the art selected for this exhibition focuses on the social and cultural impacts of these migratory patterns, their political significance, the histories of defiance and resistance, and their implications for individual and collective identities”⁶.

The first iteration of the project, creation of the VMCMM, was undertaken with the intention of making the research coming out of the project widely available not just to project stakeholders, partners and participants but to the wider diaspora interested in Caribbean migration history, culture and heritage:

“... a major research outcome that assembles digital media of cultural heritage; making it easy to access

and use. 3D digital objects, 360° museum tours and community discussion videos populate the Virtual Museum as content generated from the 3D Workshops, held in three European, three Latin American and three Caribbean countries. By creating digital content from community museums all over the world, the heritage, objects and stories can be shared and appreciated by a global audience”⁷.

The succeeding key iteration of the project was the international museums conference *Itinerant Identities: Museum Communities/Community Museums* which was successfully held at the University of the West Indies in November 2018. The conference (and its resulting publication *Communities and Museums in the 21st Century: Shared Histories and Climate Action* commissioned by ICOM Routledge press) was intended to:

“ ... gather both practitioners and thinkers from museums, academia, cultural industries, government, NGO and other entities, in order to discuss and develop new and innovative perspectives in the field of museums with respect to communities and sustainability, migration and gender, public education and audience development, the conservation of culture heritage tourism, cyber museology and digital identities, and the new museum pedagogies required to define, drive and deliver such within a knowledge society in a smart economy... provide a timely and interactive international platform to meet, discuss and debate museums and intersecting disciplines, through a range of engaging discursive and experimental gatherings. The papers ... are expected to stimulate discussion, provoke advocacy and promote action, based on cutting edge and informative presentations and interactive social events”⁸.

The next outcome of the research, and the key focus of this paper was the travelling exhibition *The Enigma of Arrival: The Politics and Poetics of Caribbean Migration to Britain* which enjoyed a prototype/test launch at the Conference in order to garner feedback from the various diasporic audiences represented. This travelling exhibition on Caribbean migration drew on the theme of “the Enigma of Arrival” as it elucidates and examines key moments in the (relatively) unknown relationship, the explained/unexplained reasons, the often unexamined periods, and at times inexplicable nuances of the transition of post war Britain as a result of the initial enthusiastic recruitment and later (apparent) rejection of loyal British citizens from its West Indian colonies who came from the late 1940s until the 1970s to support the “Mother Country’s” efforts to rebuild itself and rejuvenate its economy.

The strangely frozen picture by the surrealist painter Giorgio de Chirico, provided the original inspiration for *The Enigma of Arrival* which tells the story of a young Indian from the Caribbean arriving in post-imperial England. Naipaul’s novel is almost an autobiography - the story of a journey, from one place to another, from the British colony of Trinidad to the ancient countryside of England, and from one state of mind to another. As one critic writes: *The Enigma of Arrival* is “a strange book, more meditation than novel... Its subject is the narrator’s consciousness, its reformation by the act of migration, of ‘arrival’, and its gradual turning towards James’s ‘distinguished thing’, death”

Research in this phase of the project was centred on the historical parameters and scope of Caribbean Post-World War II migration to Britain and its legacy amongst later generations both at home and abroad. The broad exhibition themes articulated by The University of the West Indies as the basis for the research agenda included:

- *Caribbean Conditions Pre-migration* – in particular those factors and conditions inherent in Caribbean society immediately prior to the migratory movement which created an environment conducive to its occurrence
- *Arrival in the UK* – the phenomenon of the large influx of migrants from the Caribbean to the UK and the experiences engendered by this large scale migration
- *Accommodation* – documenting how Caribbean migrants were absorbed into Britain, where they went and how they were accommodated
- *Settling-in Conditions* – understanding how migrants adjusted to English society and how it adjusted to them
- *Cultural Integration* – examining how migrants were able to accept certain particulars of Britishness whilst preserving a uniquely Caribbean perspective of their own and how these two cultures merged to become modern day Britain as the impact of their presence changed British cultural norms establishing a newer more diverse definition/notion of the UK
- *Caribbean Resettlement* – examining the impact of returning nationals to the Caribbean whose British experience led them to have expectations of their native countries which precipitated growth and change within origin societies
- *Generational Experiences* – a look at those generations beyond Windrush which were themselves not necessarily migratory but whose experiences and expectations and outlook were still shaped by the migratory experiences of their fore parents

Global historical erasures have often created silences which are being challenged to ensure that inclusive stories are discovered and shared. The resurrection of such historical omissions often brings to light forgotten or erased histories in a variety of ways from examining critical archives, intangible memories and material culture, to community archive productions through accurate and

thorough interrogation of historical records. Data compilation and sharing processes provide avenues for revisionist efforts in creating authentic counter-narratives and offer new possibilities for unearthing past histories and the engagement of diverse national, regional, diasporic and global audiences. In essence the exhibition serves as something of a 'meditation' on Caribbean migration and its long memory in the identities of the region.

This large and far-reaching swathe of Caribbean history affecting multiple small island nations across the region, and involving a significant section of the Caribbean descended diaspora both in the region and abroad elsewhere in the commonwealth, was documented by multiple trajectories of research which were used together to present a multidimensional picture of the Windrush history:

- Oral histories were sought and recorded from living survivors of the Windrush experience and their descendants
- Extensive research was undertaken in the West Indies Federal Archives where original documents pertaining to the Windrush phenomenon were consulted to understand how West Indian political leadership and administration at the time viewed and interacted with the massive regional outmigration
- Critical analysis was carried out of those documents pertaining to migration which were produced for the management and assistance of the migrants who were committed to settlement in Britain in order to understand the terms and conditions under which migration was accepted and/or encouraged by the host country
- Attempts were made either by outright acquisition or loan to acquire artefacts from the period which would provide an added physical dimension to the history being documented
- Newspaper accounts of the time period were accessed to ascertain how British society viewed the migration and the migrants

- Museums and historians from across the region were invited to contribute research, content, analysis and artefacts to the project
- A lecture series was held in order to encourage additional research and foster critical discussion on the Windrush phenomenon and publicise the research to broaden its base
- Biographical research was conducted on key West Indian personalities who were products of the Windrush migration or descendants of migrants to ascertain the extent to which the migratory experience had impacted their lives as well as their subsequent contributions to British and Caribbean societies

What rapidly emerged was a complex multifaceted multi-vocal history of human experience which created a historical picture touching the lives of Caribbean people across the diaspora. That what emerged was documented history was never in doubt, but its living humanity and its ability to engage the corporeal survivors and descendants of that history was as unexpected as it was unprecedented. It is one thing to read facts and figures in a history book and quite another to hear and see the active existing voice of that history telling its own story and able to confirm and/or deny suppositions on how that experience is interpreted. Seeing photographs of welcoming slogans "Britain needs your help" counterpointed with the voices and teary eyed shared memories of racism and discrimination experienced in the British streets, homes, and work places balanced with the quiet pride of persevering despite disappointed expectations and political, social, psychological, physical and financial challenges gives history an affective dimension which is not often possible outside of deliberate fictionalisation and dramatization.

The difference here is that there can be no accusations of over-dramatisation or exaggeration for emotive effect because each experience is real and corroborated by multiple voices all still alive and able to defend and support each other's stories as well as written accounts. Further, these stories are then corroborated by the literature of the day which while not utilised as a data source in quite

the same manner as the project's other research could not be ignored, as these fictional stories were more emotively accessible, otherwise complete replicas in terms of content for the history of experiences being documented through oral histories – a case not so much of art imitating life but of art documenting life.

Curatorial Considerations

“The second thing that struck me is that this narration of history was being explored through the personal experiences and chronicles of ordinary people. This is consistent with the changing approach to the study of History which is increasingly shifting away from a narrow study of the elites and the power structures in society towards the lives of ordinary people – to the study of: women, working people, migrant families, and in this case the brave and blameless Windrush generation” (Professor Clive Landis, Remarks at the Opening of “The Enigma of Arrival: The Politics and Poetics of Caribbean Migration to Britain” Exhibition, June 21st, 2019)

In developing the *Enigma of Arrival: The Politics and Poetics of Caribbean Migration to Britain* exhibition, considerations of a community of practice were embedded within the project framework. In keeping with the evolving paradigm of museums as responsible social actors as they seek to better engage with community concerns and global challenges, *Enigma* was intended to provide new opportunities for the Caribbean region's museums and communities to co-curate previously unarticulated national/regional/bi-regional narratives. These experiences of working together to establish content, and to share images and artefacts, allowed for a community of curatorial practice approach. This curatorial framework is derived from the Lave and Wenger (1991) concept of a community of practice, which speaks to a social theory of learning through “a set of relations among persons, activity, and world, over time and in relation with other tangential and overlapping communities of practice” (98). In the exhibition

development, the team adapted this for museum practice in the following ways:

- *Collaborative Research* A preliminary research team from the University of the West Indies and the Barbados Museum & Historical Society collectively worked on developing themes that might be key in sharing the histories of the Windrush. This was conducted at all those sources located within the region which might yield the voices of those in the region administering the process.
- *Documentary Resources* One of the significant stakeholders in this process was the West Indies Federal Archives of UWI Cave Hill, who shared a collection of correspondence between the central government in London and the various colonial offices across the Caribbean region discussing policy making, accommodation conditions, and effects of the Windrush migration on local communities.
- *Oral Testimonies* Another significant collaborator, for research but also for media content, was Claude Graham and the Caribbean Broadcasting Corporation. Mr. Graham had developed a series of television programmes between the years 1990-2000, inquiring into the Windrush Generation, and particularly of the experiences of the “second generation” (children of the Windrush Generation), tackling topics of cultural identity, racism, economic mobility, repatriation and social integration. Although focussing a lens on Barbadian experiences, the breadth of programming also included diasporic stories of Antiguan and Jamaican communities. This content contributed greatly in humanizing the historical and political aspects of the Windrush Migration.
- *Co-curating content* An open call was released for communities and institutions to share objects and images in their own collections that they would like to see in the exhibition. Images received from interested persons informed the curatorial direction. After an initial review of the contents of the draft

panels and the receipt of feedback from a small group of colleagues, a community open call was circulated around the Caribbean region seeking further input from local/regional colleagues in March which was extended to international colleagues in April/May 2019.

- *Content Peer Review* The exhibition materials (mainly draft designs of the interpretive panels) were shared with professional peers for feedback on the narratives presented and imagery used.
- *Sustainable exchanges* The exhibition panels were also shared as an invitation for professional peers to host the exhibition as part of their own Windrush/migration commemorations and programming.

Figure 1: Community of Practice Cycle (based on Lave and Wenger 1991)

These experiences of working together to establish curatorial content and text, to share images and (digital) artefacts, allowed for a design process which resulted in a richer experience for communities at home and in the Diaspora and for host museums, as they shared in exploring new ways to acknowledge their routes to their roots. Through a structured dialogic process, participants explored potential collaborations and partners learned from each other, and how such human histories could be made real and relevant. More on how this was achieved is outlined below.

Exhibition Goals

- The exhibition team agreed upon specific goals for the audience for the content being researched and developed and it was anticipated that visitors to the travelling exhibition would:
 - Begin to develop an understanding of the importance of this moment in both Caribbean and British history and the formation of new relations built on that basis.
 - Understand the complexity of migration patterns and better appreciate different constructions of home and identity.
 - Understand the role of the Caribbean migrants in Britain's reconstruction and rejuvenation in the post-war era and recognize the value of its commemoration in the era of Brexit.
 - Sense the importance of the Anglophone Caribbean as sites of memory, and cultural regeneration, not only for themselves but throughout the Diaspora.
 - Reflect on how the contemporary legacies of migration affect us all and be inspired to take ownership of the shaping of personal and public histories as a result.

Research into Migration during Windrush

"I was excited to work on this project because it gave me the opportunity to put my research skills to use and also helped me to do some additional research and expounded further on an area that my undergraduate thesis was based on." - Rosalie Mayers - UWI researcher for Enigma exhibition

Research for the development of exhibition scripts was conducted for this component of the project by UWI graduate, Ms. Rosalie Mayers, commissioned specifically for the task based on her knowledge and experience of documenting the Migration of Barbadian Women to the United Kingdom during the late colonial period.

Following consultations with the exhibition team, initial draft scripts were produced during July and August and finalized during September 2018. Consultations on their contents were also held with Prof. Mary Chamberlain and Dr. Lara Putnam, both of whom have contributed significantly to the body of knowledge about this subject of Caribbean migration to Britain as evidenced by their publications¹⁰.

Editing of the text fell under the purview of the Museum's Education and Community Outreach Officer, Ms. Kaye Hall. A number of primary and secondary sources yielded some useful content and which was supplemented by audio-visual content from a series of oral history research and interviews which were being conducted by our research team amongst returning nationals and their descendants, as well as archival oral histories in the Museum's Shilstone Memorial Library.

It was noted that a number of Caribbean writers formed a part of this migratory experience to the UK and it was thought that the exhibit could benefit from the addition of a cultural dimension as expressed through excerpts of their works where appropriate. The Officer therefore completed additional research in order to match the work of these authors and other creatives to the exhibit's visual and text content. Authors/artistes included but were not limited to V S Naipaul, Samuel Selvon, Louise Bennett, E R Brathwaite, Linton Kwesi Johnson, Andrea Levy, Wallace Collins, George Lamming and Hannah Lowe.

Artefact and Image Research

During the reporting period, various methods were employed to identify artefact and image resources that could be used in the exhibition, both in the poster panels themselves and in installation displays to help tell the stories of migration. As part of the coursework for the UWI's Museum Studies M.A. Course H 6720 conducted within the Department of History and Philosophy, participants in the course were invited to develop as a graded project an exhibition design brief on the subject of Caribbean Migration to Britain. Throughout April and May 2018, the students worked on a joint exercise to identify and assemble relevant online and onsite digital and tangible documents, images, artefacts, and some sound and film recordings relevant to the production of the exhibition.

There were also initial attempts to connect with and include community materials from publics across the Caribbean region and our colleagues in Caribbean institutions. However, it became apparent that within the Caribbean museum collections on the 20th century in general, artefacts from the Windrush period and Caribbean migration in particular were minimal, and in fact the first such collection(s) would be created for display in project's exhibitions, so UK based institutions were also contacted to gather material. In addition, a wealth of images and videos were

found to be publicly available and could be used in the project provided the budget allowed the purchase of the rights to display them.

The community and diaspora, although willing to share their stories were somewhat hesitant to donate or even loan the hard-won physical mementoes of their experiences in Britain.

Figure 2 - Acc# 2013.3.146 Brown hard case valise with BOAC label

They were willing to “show and tell” but not be separated from those very personal artefacts of their experiences. This was perhaps the only “downside” to the community inclusion where so many participants had a direct experience of the history which was being documented - and indeed which is still evolving - as

Figure 3 - Cover Art, Contents Page and Foreword of “Going to Britain?” The British Broadcasting Company, 1961 Courtesy the Barbados Museum & Historical Society

Figure 4 - Cover and Excerpts from “How to Live in Britain: A Handbook for Students from Overseas”, The British Council, 1962 Courtesy of the Barbados Museum & Historical Society

their stories and hence their relationships with Britain and the Caribbean and the evolving histories of those two sovereignties are not yet over. We therefore obtained very few physical artefacts to accompany our wealth of documentary and digital media content.

During research conducted, visual materials and artefacts from the Barbados Museum & Historical Society were identified and listed. As the designated coordinator for exhibition design and development, the Museum contributed these Open Access for image reproduction for use in the exhibition panels and marketing:

1. Brown hard case valise with BOAC label (fig 2)
2. Geest Line label suitcase
3. Dark blue hard case valise
4. Going to Britain? The British Broadcasting Company, 1961 (fig 3)
5. How to Live in Britain: A Handbook for Students from Overseas, The British Council, 1962 (fig 4)

Photographs and postcard images to be considered for the Exhibition with the corresponding relevant themes were also collated and listed for consideration:

Figure 5 - BMHS Photographic Images Considered for theme 1 - Pre-Migration Socio-economic conditions – (Above) Black and white photo of barefooted, male worker bent over while checking/cleaning factory equipment; (Below) Landscape oriented photo of housing conditions in Golden Square Bridgetown circa 1930s. Courtesy the Barbados Museum & Historical Society

In addition, the London Transport Museum offered the exhibition a free license to reproduce images on the poster panels, with the proviso that they list the appropriate credit line acknowledging that museum's contribution.

Other images were identified through the Government Information Service. However, the largest collection of relevant images online that was used for the exhibition was sourced through Getty Images. Licensing

had to be purchased, and the indicative costs for licensing images formed a major part of the exhibition budget. In addition, through professional contacts the BMHS was able to identify other important image resources from the archives of UK photographers such as Syd Shelton and Neil Kenlock which complemented the other materials available.

Putting it all together

For this phase of the project we created a prototype exhibition in the online environment of the Virtual Museum of Caribbean

Figure 6a – London Transport Photographic Images (Above) Lauries Herridle and Ralph Straker, 1957

(Below) British passport issued to Mr. R O Moseley in Barbados, 1959;

Figure 6b (Left) Male bus driver and female conductor chatting by their bus; both are recent recruits from the Caribbean by Henry Grant, 1962;

(Below) Female bus driver training at Chiswick Works, circa 1970s

Opposite Page - Figure 7 - Mind Map - Enigma of Arrival Community of Curatorial Practice (based on Lave and Wenger 1991)

Migration and Memory in order to gauge community and visitors' reactions and demonstrate clear progress to the community and others. The exhibition script and preliminary designs were therefore completed with a view to launching via this medium.

The exhibition team after a two-month period reviewed the results of this process of community consultation. Other members of UWI team, the Caribbean museum community and advisors were then invited afterwards to review revised content and provide written comments on the exhibition before it was finalized with the project designer, and with lenders to the exhibition to finalize artefacts which were to be displayed.

The exhibition prototype was launched digitally within the Virtual Museum of Caribbean Migration and Memory during the International Museums Conference at UWI Cave Hill Barbados from November 5th to 11th, 2018. This comprised of touch screen navigation and a portal for visitors to submit feedback and their own stories of migration, thus being inclusive of community input, and meeting our target of co-curatorship. The virtual content of the exhibition also included a selection of the poster panels in digital form, as well as related videos and digitized documents identified as part of the research undertaken. Some 3D renderings of related artefacts were also included.

This launch was extremely well received by conference participants, community museums and researchers, providing both much needed encouragement and invaluable feedback for the exhibit itself, as well as for the community of practice model which was being implemented. The exhibition development thereafter manifested, and was maintained, as a cyclical model of research following the established model based on Lave and Wenger's (1991) Community of curatorial practice yielding the self-sustaining exhibit *The Enigma of Arrival: The Politics and Poetics of Caribbean Migration to Britain* which continues to develop and grow as it travels across the diaspora, adding

research and content and broadening its reach through its very existence and its associated programming.

The formal exhibit was launched on July 21st, the eve of Windrush day 2019, and was twice extended by popular request from the Ministry of the Creative Economy, Culture and Sports of the Government of Barbados, in addition to multiple requests from across the school network, beyond its intended closure of October 2019 to the end of that year. It has since then travelled variously evolving and expanding with each additional curatorial perspective:

Digital Iterations

“The response we have received has been overwhelmingly positive. The evidence of our digital analytics shows that the exhibition and community programme led to more than 9,000 visits to our website, as well as reaching tens of thousands of people across social media. This encourages us to think about the ways in which our exhibition programme can be complemented in the future with similarly ambitious and creative digital offers. We have been encouraged to see that our audience extends far beyond our town’s boundaries and that by harnessing advances in digital communications to collaborate with colleagues across oceans, we will be enhancing possibility for further understanding and exchange.” (Brendan Carr, Community Engagement Curator, Reading Museum.)

Through the Centre for Caribbean and Diaspora Studies, the digital poster exhibition *Enigma of Arrival* was installed at the Rutherford Building Library at Goldsmiths University (October 2019). This digital iteration aimed to complement activities and a symposium within UK Black History Month programming, to assist in raising awareness on this part of shared British-Caribbean history with students and staff. The display element of the exhibition was through the Virtual Museum of Caribbean

Migration and Memory, showcasing exhibition panel artwork archived online.

A second digital iteration was exhibited by Reading Museum (June 2020), which had a different approach. The team there worked in close collaboration with a Caribbean community committee formed out of the Windrush Foundation, as well as with the exhibition team from the BMHS and UWI Museum. Existing content from *Enigma* was integrated directly into the Reading Museum website, with additional content co-created with the Reading community such as video recordings and educational materials. This virtual exhibit was launched for Windrush Day, July 22nd 2020 and was accompanied by local programming support activities including a radio broadcast featuring music from the Windrush period as well as interviews of the Windrush migrants and their descendants who shared their experiences of living and working in Britain during the period¹¹.

A third digital iteration arose out of the collaborative model employed by Reading Museum. The Black Professional Network Vodafone hosted the Virtual Museum of Migration and Memory on the Vodafone UK intranet as a part of their Windrush Day celebrations (June – July 2020). This was of particular importance to them not only in sharing of some of their own heritage, but of educating their colleagues about this important aspect of Britain’s history. Access was free to all of Vodafone UK’s 11,500 employees.

This additional engagement with the exhibition was led by Mr. Rodney Harewood who was a part of the community committee for Reading Museum’s exhibition team. His role within that committee was to foster greater connections between the Reading Museum and the Caribbean community which was of particular interest in the Barbados-Reading connection. Hosting a subsequent iteration of this exhibition in Reading speaks to how a community of curatorial practice encourages community groups to take ownership of the exhibition content and narratives,

and share them in new ways and with new networks that are not in direct contact with the core exhibition team.

Community Interaction

There was a community-led iteration of the *Enigma* exhibition in Birmingham by the 2nd Generation Barbadians and Friends Association (December 2019). This was completely organized by community members and aimed at providing a space to commemorate this shared history within their community.

Institutional Installation

... the exhibition's timing was very relevant and one of the things that we did was that along with the poetry and the music and the spoken word archive we actually engaged other museums within our community. One of the issues I think that we had to navigate was the collection based elements of it... to effectively represent the Windrush experience.

... one of the things that I did in partnership with the National Museum of Jamaica was that ...they [had] suitcases, trunks, but colloquially in Jamaican terms its referred to as a dulcimina I was shocked because we had some (visitors) who came in that had never heard that term...

..., it told me that I'd taken some things for granted in terms of how knowledge had been transferred.

....we also got on loan from the Imperial War Museum, the footage, the World War Two documentary about Caribbean nationals to Britain and very often people only see the first few minutes with Una Marson reflecting, introducing the BBC and introducing a great cricketer and then you'll see them dancing and that's usually cut ...

People were fascinated, they were drawing up chairs ...and watching ... you want to show people... that the history of migration is such a fundamental part of Caribbean

identity - and the fact that we're dealing with issues with the Windrush generation is... it's very contemporary and we can feel strongly about it but it's part of the legacy of the push-pull relationship between the Caribbean and the former, Imperial nations. (Shani Roper-Edwards, Curator, The UWI Museum, The University of the West Indies Mona Campus, Kingston,) Jamaica) [Interview with Exhibit Team, by B. Carr, Reading Museum, June 2020]

The UWI Museum, Mona Campus, hosted an iteration of the *Enigma* exhibition from February 7th 2020. The keynote at the opening was Dr. Hilary Robertson Hickling who has written extensively on the mental health of Caribbean migrants to Britain and spearheaded the programme 'Dat time in Farin' which featured Caribbean migrants to Britain sharing their experiences. This exhibit has also been extended by popular request.

Programming and Public Dissemination

An integral part of sustaining this model of community of curatorial practice was the programme of public awareness and education activities surrounding the development of the exhibition. This ongoing programme included an active social media campaign and continuing public outreach and communication as well as some specifically targeted activities which were intended to engage public interest and engender lasting relationships with our research, collections, documentation and exhibition initiatives

These included:

1. A lecture series held from March to May of 2019 entitled "From Invitation to Deportation: 70 Years of the Windrush Generation"
2. "Windrush" a theatrical programme aimed at developing applied theatre arts as a medium for historical interrogation and dissemination

3. Online Engagement as a tool for maintaining contact with our various communities
4. Ongoing Discourses which contribute to the sustainability of the cross fertilisation of research, interrogation and ideas

Lecture Series

The lecture series was conceptualised as a framework to encourage discussion of the emerging themes from the Windrush research as well as explore the diasporic response to these themes and the history they represented. The series was very well received by the public as evidenced by the hundreds who attended the lectures in the series, as well as those who viewed them online where they remained after the events themselves. In addition, they yielded rich discourse from the lecturers' research and lived experiences, as well as statistical information and video content not previously encountered during the project's initial research. Audience interaction included anecdotes shared during the discussion sessions which followed each lecture, oral history interviews which were added to the exhibition content where appropriate, and ongoing social media engagement and have generated sufficient interest that they have been featured elsewhere. Last, but by no means least, a book of essays based on their content is planned and already in its editing stages. All of this has of course contributed to the body of knowledge generated by the exhibit and the research project but are also a demonstration of the sustainability of the subject material in terms of relevance and as history which is still being written and documented.

Applied Theatre Practice as a Tool for Community Education

"This piece is important to me, because I am, I don't want to say directly affected, but my family is kind of involved in that Windrush era. My great-grandparents went down during

the Windrush and that led to me and my other family members being born in England. So for me it's more of a case where I'm thinking wow, this is so unfair because that could have been my grandparents that could have been my mum, that could have been me, being sent back to a place that they don't really call home, when they call England their home instead." (Dylan Collymore, theatre student at the Barbados Community College)

An early trend which emerged from our research was a visible and obvious correlation to real life documented experiences of migration from the Windrush period and the literary and other cultural expressions generated by the immigrants who had lived and worked in Britain. Not only were these experiences used in the exhibit to infuse its panels with an additional layer of humanity for those who would experience it in its various forms, but it provided the opportunity for young practitioners to explore the phenomenon as a historical fact in and of itself, and examine its relevance to Caribbean society today.

Applied Theatre is defined as theatre which goes beyond the merely distantly performative to the inclusive and interactive. It expects to be a force which interacts with the sociocultural entity which constitutes its audience and presumes to effect some sort of change by its existence. Pendergast and Saxton (2009, p 6) describe such theatre as not carrying any "limiting fixed agendas" whilst falling outside of mainstream "played in spaces that are not usually defined as theatre buildings, with participants who may or may not be skilled in theatre arts and to audiences who have a vested interest in the issue taken up by the performance or are members of the community addressed by the performance".

History in the Caribbean has a unique relationship with its audience, because many persons in these communities have learned their history through the filter of an education based on a colonial framework which, for the most part, excludes the voices of their direct antecedents, providing a Eurocentric perspective which often leaves audiences disassociated with their national

histories. The job of the modern historian and by extension modern museums is to reinterpret that history in a manner which gives voice to the experiences of the ancestors of those who now form the bulk of the communities and audiences and which do not reflect the views inherent in previous colonial governance and history. Such interpretation has its roots in the Lave and Wenger (1991) concept of a community of practice, participatory museum models (such as Simon, 2010; Diamantopoulou, Insulander, & Lindstrand, 2012) and social responsibility of museums (Hooper-Greenhill 1992, Sandell, 2002, Vawda, 2019).

The resulting collaborative project between the UWI/BMHS project partners and the theatre arts students of Barbados Community College's Performing Arts Programme yielded not just a spectacular Windrush performance developed by the student/practitioners which is now documented as part of the VMCM, but a number of positive results for youth involved in the programme:

- Student/developers improved their research skills particular with regard to oral history and interpretation under the guidance of the programme – sustainable skills which will continue to infuse their performing practice and influence their interrogation of the histories they portray
- Student/developers honed their skills in applied theater as a tool for exploring sociological and historical phenomenon and their effects on the development of people and culture whilst the museum benefited from the use of its space as a place for social responsibility (Hooper-Greenhill 1992, Sandell, 2002, Vawda, 2019)
- Student/developers working within the project have expressed repeatedly how much more connected they feel to this part of their heritage than previously because the nature of the project facilitated the examination of their culture and heritage from a personal perspective – they learned that this history is neither distant or someone else's but very

personal to Caribbean people as it is not just a history of the past but also of the present

- Student/developers have also indicated rapid expansion of knowledge of National and Caribbean history and heritage as well as an awareness that our history is not a simple recording of events but a living, breathing, constantly evolving interpretation of those events with varying perspectives
- Student/developers have expressed growing interest in both expanding their knowledge of history and heritage through formal programmes and individual research, but also a growing commitment to continue learning even if they work outside the field of heritage in later years, as well as a desire to support the dissemination heritage knowledge to their peers

In addition, the Museum itself benefitted in a number of concrete ways from inclusion of this community-focused activity which reinforced the role of the museum as an active participant and actor in community-based activism and change – as Hooper Greenhill's socially responsible Museum connected with and relevant to its audiences and their interests through the following:

- Provision of another avenue for creatives to develop their craft with a real world live paying audience for their work at the end of the development process
- Interaction of creatives directly with heritage through the Museum, its people and its collections to build awareness and hopefully to influence their creative work by this interaction
- Creation of the opportunity to practice and/or participate in elements of our intangible cultural heritage through, storytelling, dancing, playing traditional games, etc.

- Expansion of the Museum's offerings for its younger audiences by the introduction of an interactive educational programming element
- Creation of additional public education/programming elements around the Museum's topical temporary exhibition schedules
- Facilitation of ongoing requests from existing Museum audiences with challenges of visiting during regular museum hours for weeknight and weekend events that they could attend
- Re-vitalizing the Museum as a popular theatre space in Barbados

Online Engagement

It was decided relatively early in the process that it would encourage continued engagement and interaction with our community both at home and abroad if the project was active on social media, both for communicating with migrants and researchers and for keeping the general public informed about the project's progress. This process was begun through the calls for collaborators and donors and continued with the sharing of programming content such as the lecture series online and online blogging. As audiences have become aware of the availability of this content the following on the social media where it is being hosted has increased as has the demand for more and similar content.

This strategy became even more relevant and essential after the spread of the Corona virus severely limited physical programming around both the exhibition and its associated public education initiatives from March of 2020. Physical iterations of the exhibit were quickly and rapidly modified to provide access to online audiences, converting the physical launch planned for Reading Museum, for example, to an online launch and exhibit. This

quick response engendered by the already existing social media and online iterations of the exhibition elsewhere has enabled the team to reposition and enhance the dissemination strategy for the exhibition and associated programming. Thus it has expanded to provide additional content on various social media platforms, which now include the added element of interactive activities associated with the exhibition and opportunities for visitors to share their memories and stories of migration and join the community which is ever building, sharing and exhibiting the body of knowledge around the Windrush phenomenon.

Ongoing Discourses

Programming has also yielded a number of opportunities to discuss the co-curatorial practice which has underpinned this process as well as the content and knowledge development which has resulted (and which continues to grow) from it. These ongoing discussions consisting of video interviews, webinar presentations, Windrush radio broadcasts and social gatherings for thematic discussion such as the BMHS Windrush Tea and Conversations Event in November 2019 as well as the "Itinerant Identities" Conference in November 2018 have all continued to yield useful content and sustain the continued investigation, exploration, analysis and growth of the body of knowledge on the Windrush phenomenon. The team continues to receive and facilitate these requests and has noted that as the exhibition continues to travel and demonstrate the sustainability of the interest in its subject matter, so too it continues to drive interest in the community of practice curatorial model under which it has been developed – and is continuing to develop and has welcomed the feedback and interest as a demonstration of the sustainability of the model to facilitate ongoing cyclical research and development of exhibits and programming as well as ongoing historical research which privileges community memory over western/center/global North narratives.

Conclusion

All of these elements of sustainability point to the viability of the idea of the community of practice as a workable model for the development of small and medium sized community focused museums in remote rural and island settings. The *Enigma of Arrival* has been a prototype with a far-reaching impact which points to the ongoing viability of the subject matter as a history of which we have barely scratched the surface which is suitable for more and deeper exploration and analysis. By the same token, the community of practice too has proven itself as the model for the progressive 21st century Caribbean museum to utilize in the quest to remain relevant and meaningful in an increasingly individual and digital world where personal stories and the savvy to effectively disseminate content widely across a variety of media matter, and the Barbados Museum & Historical Society is demonstrably its best case study thus far.

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ENDNOTES

- 1 European Union Latin America and Caribbean Museums - a consortium of academics, museum professionals and policy makers working in Scotland, Portugal, Spain, France, Peru, Chile, Costa Rica and the West Indies who are committed to community museology making a difference in the world, conceived under the auspices of ICOM (the International Council of Museums: <http://icom.museum>) in 2014. For more information see <https://eulacmuseums.net/index.php/partnership-2>
- 2 EULAC Museums – Home <https://eulacmuseums.net/index.php/73-news-front-1>
- 3 EULAC Museums Project Deliverables by Work Package <https://eulacmuseums.net/index.php/detail-2#wp7>
- 4 EULAC Museums – Home <https://eulacmuseums.net/index.php/73-news-front-1>
- 5 VMCM – www.eu-lac.org/vmcarib
- 6 Arrivants – Press Release, Arrivants: Making Exhibitions in the Caribbean, Reflections from the Curatorial Team <https://arrivantsexhibition.wordpress.com/2018/11/01/the-journey-begins/>
- 7 EULAC Museums, Resources, Virtual Museum <https://eulacmuseums.net/index.php/resources/virtual-museum-2>
- 8 International Museum Conference Website <https://eulacmuseumsconference2018.wordpress.com/about-us/>
- 9 Review of V.S. Naipaul's 1987 novel, *The Enigma of Arrival* in "A Sad Pastoral", *The Guardian*, 13 March 1987
- 10 The below bibliography details resources used in researching migration during the Windrush period, that informed the exhibition panel texts:
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 - Black Cultural Archive. War to Windrush https://static1.squarespace.com/static/5a01baa7d7bdcee985c80c15/t/5a088583f9619a1bb0097aa7/1510507909587/2016_Windrush-V1.0.pdf
- 11 Link to Readings exhibit is available until October 2020 at <https://www.readingmuseum.org.uk/resources/windrush-day/windrush-day-enigma-arrival>